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**POLISH PROPER NAMES DERIVED FROM A LATIN
MYTHOLOGICAL NAME¹**

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Abstract

The research object of the present text is represented by Polish proper names, derived from a Roman mythological name. The authors' aim is to present a full list of them and their initial meaning. The researched anthroponyms are divided into two groups according to the type of the appellative used as a base during the process of derivation and canonization by the Catholic church, the Orthodox one, or by both of them.

Keywords: *Polish proper name, Roman mythological name, derivation, canonization, anthroponym*

Rezumat

În articol, se supun cercetării numele proprii de origine poloneză, derivate de la nume mitologice latine. Scopul autoarelor este să dea o listă amplă a acestora, cu indicația semnificației lor inițiale. Antroponimele analizate sunt împărțite în două clase, în acord cu tipurile de apelativ, utilizat ca bază formativă în procesul de derivare și canonizare de Biserica Catolică, Ortodoxă sau de ambele în același timp.

Cuvinte-cheie: *nume propriu polonez, nume mitologic latinesc, derivare, canonizare, antroponim*

The existence of mythological texts would not be possible without the names of the characters included in them – quite often the etymological link between the name and the appellative used for its derivation is obvious and linked with the story topic.

The more popular a certain mythological text is, the more popular the names that belong to it are. This is the reason why they have become part of almost all contemporary anthropological systems and are still used today as personal names.

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The research object of the present article is represented by 3 masculine Polish personal names and 9 feminine ones, derived from a Roman mythological name.

They are classified in accordance to the basic appellative used for their derivation. The authors' main aim is to follow the initial etymology because, due to different reasons, it is possible that their genuine meaning may not be quite transparent. Very often it is influenced by associations made with other lexemes similar in pronunciation but part of a modern language, i.e. the appearance of the so called "folk etymology".

An additional extralinguistic classification is presented in accordance to the information about a name usage as a saint's name.

I. Polish proper names classification according to the basic derivation appellative

1. Masculine Polish proper names, derived from Roman mythological names coined from a common noun: Janus (< Ianus/ Janus < *ianus*, *i*, *m* - "covered; door"); Sylwan (< Silvanus < *silva*, *ae*, *f* - "wood");
2. Masculine Polish proper names, derived from Roman mythological names with uncertain etymology: Saturn (< Saturnus < 1) unknown meaning; 2) *satur*, *ura*, *urum* - "fruitful"; 3) *sero*, *1* - "sow"; 4) *sator*, *oris*, *m* - "sower");
3. Feminine Polish proper names, derived from Roman mythological names coined from a common noun: Gracja (< Gratia < *gratia*, *ae*, *f* - "grace, beauty"); Konkordia (< Concordia < *concordia*, *ae*, *f* - "harmony; agreement");
4. Feminine Polish proper names, derived from Roman mythological names with uncertain etymology: Aurora (< Aurora < 1) *aurora*, *ae*, *f* - "dawn"; 2) *aura*, *ae*, *f* - "breeze"); Diana (< Deana/ Deviana/ Diana/ Diviana < 1) Indo-European root with the meaning of "divine"; 2) *deus*, *i*, *m* - "god"; 3) *diviana* - "divine" (feminine form of the adjective *divianus*, 3 - "divine"); 4) *diva* - "divine" (feminine form of the adjective *divus*, 3 - "divine"); 5) *dies*, *ei*, *m*/ *f* - "day"); Felicyta (< Felicitas < 1) *felicitas*, *tatis*, *f* - "luck; happiness"; 2) *felix*, *icis* - "happy"); Flora (< Flora < 1) *flos*, *oris*, *m* - "flower" ; 2) *florens*, *entis* - "blooming"); Nonna (< Nona/ Nonna < 1) Roman prenomens *Nonnus*/ *Nonus*; 2) *nona* - "ninth" (feminine form of the adjective *nonus*, 3 - "ninth"); 3) *nonna*, *ae*, *f* - "nun"); Roma (< Roma < 1) masculine personal name *Roma*; 2) *Roma*, the name of the Roman goddess, patron of Rome; 3) *Roma*, *ae*, *f* - "Rome"); Wiktoria (< Victoria < 1) Latin cognomen *Victor*; 2) Latin cognomen *Victorius*; 3) *Victoria*, the name of the Roman goddess of victory (< *victoria*, *ae*, *f* - "victory").

From the classification presented above it is obvious that two main groups are formed for both the masculine and feminine Polish proper names - Polish anthroponyms derived from Roman mythological names, coined from a common noun and from a Roman mythological name with uncertain

etymology. Regarding the male onyms, the first group is bigger; as for the female ones, the bigger group is the second.

II. Classification according to the extralinguistic information about the name canonization

1. Masculine Polish anthroponyms being names of saints canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church: *Saturn, Sylwan*;
2. Feminine Polish anthroponyms which as names of saints canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church: *Aurora, Diana, Felicyta, Flora, Gracja, Konkordia, Nonna, Wiktoria*.

All the researched anthroponyms represent saints' names canonized by both the Orthodox and the Catholic church with only one exception for the masculine onyms, *Janus*, and the feminine ones – *Roma*.

Conclusion

Polish anthroponyms are derived from Roman mythological names, coined from a common noun and from a Roman mythological name with uncertain etymology. In relation to the male onyms, the first group is bigger, while concerning the female onyms, the bigger group is the second one.

Index of the Polish proper names, derived from a Roman mythological name

Masculine anthroponyms

JANUS (K)² - Masculine proper name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Ianus/ Janus*, initially god of light and the sun, coined from *ianus, i, m* - "covered; door" (B, M2, O, S). Later on, the god is accepted as a patron of all the paths and ways as well as of the new beginning (B, G, M2, S);

SATURN (K) - Masculine proper name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Saturnus*, the god of agriculture (B, BTN, G, N, M2, O, S) with unknown meaning (BTN) or coined from *satur, ura, urum* - "fruitful" (K), *sero, 1* - "sow"(M2) or *sator, oris, m* - "sower" (S). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

SYLWAN (K) - Masculine proper name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Silvanus*, Roman god of woods and fields (B, BTN, G, M2, N, O, S), coined from *silva, ae, f* - "wood" (BTN, G, K, M2, N, S). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

Feminine anthroponyms

²The following abbreviations are used in the index for the sources of information: B = Batakliiev, 1979; BTN = www.behindthename.com; G = Grimal, 1990; H = Hensen, 2004; K = Knappová, 1985; M1 = Mifai norodov mira (Entziklopediya v dvuh tomah), t. 1 (A-K); M2 = Mifai norodov mira (Entziklopediya v dvuh tomah), t. 2 (K-YA); N = Nemirovskij, 2004; O = *Oxford Latin Dictionary*; S = Superanskaya, 1998.

AURORA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Aurora*, goddess of dawn, equivalent of the Greek goddess *Eos* (H, G, M1, S), coined from *aurora, ae, f* - "dawn" (H, G, K) or *aura, ae, f* - "breeze" (M1). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

DIANA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Deana/ Deviana/ Diana/ Diviana*, goddess of hunting, moon, woods, and giving birth, equivalent of the Greek goddess *Artemis* (BTN, H, G, M1, O, S), coined from the Indo-European root "divine" (BTN), *deus, i, m* - "god" (K), *diviana* - "divine" (feminine form of the adjective *divianus, 3* - "divine"), *diva* - "divine" (feminine form of the adjective *divus, 3* - "divine") (O) or *dies, ei, m/ f* - "day". A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

FELICYTA (BTN) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Felicitas*, goddess of the good luck and happiness (BTN, M2), coined from *felicitas, tatis, f* - "luck, happiness" (BTN, S) or *felix, icis* - "happy". A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox (BTN, S) and the Catholic church (BTN);

FLORA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Flora*, goddess of flowers, blooming and spring (BTN, G, M2, O, S), coined from *flos, oris, m* - "flower" (BTN, K, M2) or *florens, entis* - "blooming". A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

GRACJA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Gratia*, goddess of beauty, coined from *gratia, ae, f* - "grace, beauty" (S). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and the Catholic church (S);

KONKORDIA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Concordia*, goddess of harmony, peace, serenity, and agreement (BTN, M1, S), patron of family life, coined from *concordia, ae, f* - "harmony, agreement" (BTN, S). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and Catholic church (S);

NONNA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Nona/ Nonna*, goddess of pregnancy (BTN, O, S), coined from the Latin prenomen *Nonnus/ Nonus* (BTN, O), *nona* - "ninth" (feminine form of the adjective *nonus, 3* - "ninth") (because of the 9 months as a normal pregnancy period) (BTN, K, S) or *nonna, ae, f* - "nun" (S). The onym is traditionally given to the ninth child in a given family or to a child born in the ninth month of the year (BTN, S). A saint's name canonized by the Orthodox and Catholic church (S);

ROMA (K) - A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name *Roma*, goddess who is a patron of Rome or coined from the name of the city itself - *Roma, ae, f* - "Rome" (G, M2, O);

WIKTORIA (BTN, K) – A feminine personal name, derived from a Roman mythological name, goddess of victory, coined from *victoria*, *ae, f* – “victory” (BTN, S). It is possible the personal name to be formed from the Latin cognomina *Victor* or *Victorius* (BTN). A saint’s name canonized by the Orthodox (BTN, S) and Catholic church (BTN).

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